

1 **Micellar Enhanced Chromatographic Separation of Selected Hazardous Chemical**
2 **Present in Hair Dye and their Detection in Formulations, Swab Including Assessment of**
3 **Damage Caused to Cuticle of Hair Shaft**

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25 **Abstract**

26 Hydroquinone (HQ), resorcinol (RS), m-aminophenol (m-AMP) and p-phenylenediamine (p-
27 PPD) are aromatic compounds which are generally used in hair dyes to provide different
28 colours to hair. In European Union the concentrations of HQ, RS, m-AMP and p-PPD is
29 regulated in hair dyes and other cosmetic products by EU commission regulation EU/2019/831.
30 This legislation is generally exercised because all these compounds are toxic and may cause
31 severe allergies when used regularly. However in India no such regulations exist to monitor
32 these toxic compounds in hair dyes therefore in this study a simple, rapid, economical and
33 ecofriendly micellar liquid chromatographic (MLC) technique has been developed which can
34 monitor all the selected toxic compounds simultaneously. HQ and RS are positional isomers
35 and are difficult to be separated by HPLC whereas with the developed MLC method it was
36 well separated and detected. The developed MLC technique has been applied to detect and
37 quantify selected analytes in oxidative and non-oxidative hair dyes and swab samples from the
38 scalp. The simultaneous separation of selected analytes was performed in mobile phase 0.09
39 M SDS, 0.01 M NaH₂PO₄-2% v/v 1-butanol at pH 7 running through C₁₈ column under
40 isocratic mode at 1 mL/min. flow rate. All the analytes were eluted within 6 min. The present
41 method has been validated following the EURCHEM Guideline, 2014 in terms of calibration
42 range (0.08-15 µg/mL), limit of detection (0.01-0.08 µg/mL), limit of quantification (0.08-0.18
43 µg/mL), accuracy (<5.6%), precision (91-105%) and robustness (<5.8%). The selected
44 compounds in hair dye formulation were found in the range of 0.09-253 µg/mL. Hair dyes
45 persistence study was conducted up to 10 days from the day of application on the scalp,
46 suggesting that the dyes were not completely washed off and were retained on the scalp for
47 more than one week. SEM analysis of dyed hair revealed that hairs are severely damaged due
48 to use of dyes. The advantage of the developed method is that it could easily be adopted by
49 quality control and cosmetic laboratories for quality control and check for the simultaneous
50 separation of positional isomers together with two other aromatic compounds.

51 **Keywords:** Hair, Hair Dyes, Micellar Liquid Chromatography, Scanning Electron Microscope

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58 **1. Introduction**

59 Irrespective of age and gender, changing the natural colour of hair is quite prevalent all
60 over the world. In the past few years, the global demand for hair dyes has increased at an
61 exponential rate. As per the CAGR (compound annual growth rate) report, the hair dyes market
62 could reach up to 42 billion dollars by 2025 [1]. The dyes used for colouring hairs are either
63 oxidative (permanent) or non-oxidative (semipermanent, temporary) in nature [2]. Chemically
64 speaking hair dyes use primary intermediates [m-aminophenol (m-AMP), p-aminophenol (p-
65 AMP), p-phenylenediamine (p-PPD), m-phenylenediamine (m-PPD), resorcinol (RS)),
66 couplers [hydroquinone (HQ), 1-naphthol (1NpOH)] and oxidizing agents (hydrogen peroxide,
67 ammonia) which react together to form a coloured dye molecule.

68 Primary intermediates generally used in hair dyes are derivatives of aromatic rings like
69 diamines, aminophenol, phenols, benzene and naphthol while couplers are the compounds that
70 provide a chemical bond between oxidizer and primary intermediate. In case of oxidative hair
71 dyes, hair colour persists for a longer duration due to penetration of small molecules of the dye
72 into hair cortex and thus are known as permanent hair dyes [3]. On the other hand, non-
73 oxidative hair dyes last only for few weeks as the dye molecule is big and cannot penetrate the
74 cortex which generally gets trapped in the cuticle. As the dye molecules are attached to the hair
75 shaft, they get washed away and are thus termed as temporary hair dyes. During the hair dyeing
76 process, the hair dyes also get absorbed through the scalp and enter the systemic circulation.
77 This is possible due to the fact that the hair are attached to the dermis of the scalp and the hair
78 follicles are in contact with blood vessels [4]. Talking about the harmful constituents present
79 in hair dyes the primary intermediate used in hair dyes have been reported as allergen,

80 carcinogen and mutagen in several in-vitro and in-vivo studies [5]. Although different allergic
81 and sensitive compounds are also present in hair dyes but allergy patch tests have been done
82 only for p-PPD [6]. As per European Union regulation (EU/2019/831) the hair dye preparations
83 containing p-PPD must mention about its allergic nature on the product wrapper or packing
84 [7]. However, in order to increase the popularity of their products, some manufacturers do not
85 indicate these allergens on product wrappers [8]. Regulatory authorities worldwide have
86 established strict cosmetics regulations due to the potential health risk of exposure to toxic hair
87 dye components [9]. Therefore in the present work, only those compounds were selected which
88 are most commonly used and classified as non-permitted dyes by EU/2019/831 i.e., HQ (pKa,
89 4.3; log P, 1.32), RS (pKa, 9.9; log P, 0.6), p-PPD (pKa, 5.4; log P, -0.25) and m-AMP (pKa,
90 5.4; log P, 0.04) [7]. Many analytical methods have been reported for the determination of non-
91 permitted and prohibited compounds in hair dyes formulation [5], wastewater [10], urine and
92 serum [11] using different chromatographic techniques like thin layer chromatography (TLC)
93 [12], gas chromatography (GC) [13], high-performance thin layer chromatography (HPTLC)
94 [14] and high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) coupled with UV-visible detector,
95 electrochemical, fluorescence [15] photodiode array (PDA), amperometric detector [16] or
96 mass spectrometry detection [17]. Among all these techniques, HPLC-PDA is a method of
97 choice by cosmetic industries and regulatory laboratories for routine analysis of selected
98 compounds but the main problem with this method is that it is not suitable for simultaneous
99 determination and separation of positional isomers [18]. In order to overcome this problem
100 micellar liquid chromatography coupled to a photodiode array detector (MLC-PDA) could be
101 a good choice which uses a hybrid mobile phase of water, surfactants and short-chain alcohols.
102 Separation in MLC is slightly different from the HPLC due to the interaction of analyte with
103 sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) modified stationary phase, micelles, hydro-organic bulk mobile
104 phase, electrostatic, dipole-dipole and proton donor-acceptor interactions [19]. The advantages

105 of MLC are its eco-friendly nature, reduction of sample preparation steps other than filtration,
106 low concentration of organic solvent used, thus reducing the time and cost of analysis [20].

107 Therefore in the present work MLC method has been developed for the simultaneous
108 determination of HQ, RS, p-PPD and m-m-AMP in hair dye formulations and swab obtained
109 from scalp obtained from volunteers who dyed their hair. It has also been studied that the hair
110 treated with different colouring agents also damages the cuticle scales and root of the hair. In
111 the present work apart from analyzing the selected compounds by chromatographic technique
112 the hair shaft and root were physically examined using a scanning electron microscope (SEM)
113 to assess the damage caused by the chemicals present in hair dyes.

114 **2. Material and methods**

115 **2.1. Standard and reagents**

116 HQ, RS, p-PPD and m-AMP was procured from Sigma Aldrich (Mumbai, India).
117 Oxidative and non-oxidative hair dyes were purchased from the local market of Sagar (Madhya
118 Pradesh, India). Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS >99%) and sodium dihydrogen phosphate
119 (NaH_2PO_4) were purchased from Himedia Laboratories Private Limited (Mumbai, India).
120 HPLC grade 1-propanol, 1-butanol and 1-pentanol were provided by Rankem, RFCL Limited
121 (New Delhi, India).

122 **2.2. Instrumentation and software**

123 The MLC system consists of a Shimadzu Prominence HPLC (Kyoto, Japan), an
124 isocratic system coupled with a PDA (SPD-M20 A; 190-800 nm) detector and the data analysis
125 was carried out using LC Solution software version 1.22 SP1. For chromatographic separation,
126 a C_{18} column of 250 mm length, 4.6 mm internal diameter, 5 μm particle size from Phenomenex
127 HyperClone™ (California, USA) was used. Mobile phase was pumped through the column at

128 a flow rate at 1 mL/min. and the injection volume of 20 μ L was used for all chromatographic
129 analyses.

130 An analytical balance Mettler-Toledo ME204 (Pocklington, United Kingdom) was used
131 for weighing standard and real samples. The pH measurements were performed using a
132 Contech LAB pH meter, Model pH-103 (Mumbai, India) equipped with a combined
133 Ag/AgCl/glass electrode. The magnetic stirrer and the ultrasonic bath were purchased from
134 PCI Analytics (Mumbai, India). Type-I ultrapure water obtained using Indion LAB Q Ultra
135 system (Mumbai, India) was used to prepare mobile phase, standard and real samples.

136 The MLC system was equipped with LC-solution software version 1.22 SP1 used for
137 data acquisition. The chromatographic data were treated using Microsoft Excel (version, 2010)
138 and Origin Pro (version 8.1).

139 **2.3. Scanning electron microscope and condition**

140 A SEM of FIE consisting of vacuum system, sample navigation, electron optics,
141 scanning system and optics was used to find out the damage caused to the hair shaft due to the
142 use of hair dyes. Morphological characterization of hair shaft was carried out by SEM (NOVA
143 NANO SEM450, FEI) at 2000X under continuous scanning voltage (15 kV). Moisture-free
144 hair samples were coated with silver and spread uniformly on conductive adhesive tape for
145 SEM analysis.

146 **2.4. Chromatographic solution preparation**

147 **2.4.1. Preparation of standard solution**

148 The mobile phases for chromatographic analysis were prepared by accurately weighing
149 surfactant (SDS) and buffer salt (NaH_2PO_4) which were then dissolved in Type-I ultrapure
150 water with the help of sonication. Depending on the composition of mobile phase a small
151 portion of organic solvent was added and the mobile phase was made up to the desired volume

152 using Type-I ultrapure water. The mobile phase was ultrasonicated for 5 min. and then filtered
153 through a 0.45 µm nylon membrane filter (Axiva, New Delhi, India) with the help of a vacuum
154 pump.

155 Individual stock solutions containing 100 mg/L of HQ, RS, p-PPD and m-AMP were
156 prepared by accurately weighing the analytes and dissolving them in Type-I ultrapure water.

157 **2.4.2 Sample collection and preparation of marketed hair dyes formulation**

158 Hair dyes (oxidative and non-oxidative) were purchased from general stores at Sagar
159 (Madhya Pradesh, India). 200 mg of oxidative (the base and oxidizer/coupler were mixed in
160 prescribed proportion before weighing) or non-oxidative formulation was diluted with 5 mL of
161 mobile phase. After that, it was filtered through 0.45 µm nylon membrane filter and directly
162 injected into the chromatographic system.

163 **2.4.3. Hair sample collection and preparation for SEM**

164 Five volunteers named in roman from I-V belonging to the research group were selected
165 for the present study. Volunteers 'I' (oxidative), 'II' and 'III' (non-oxidative) regularly used hair
166 dye, while volunteers 'IV' and 'V' never used them. Questionnaires were filled by volunteers
167 regarding age, gender, hair dye, hair oil, shampoo used and the frequency of their application
168 and use etc. Hair samples were collected from the middle part of the scalp. All collected
169 samples were packed into zip-lock polybags and stored at room temperature. The collected
170 samples were further analyzed by SEM to know the damage caused by the selected analytes on
171 hair shaft morphology. Before SEM analysis hair shaft was washed with Type-I ultrapure water
172 and shampoo to remove adhered dust and dirt. After washing, the hair samples were dried at
173 room temperature and 1 cm long hair strand and hair root with bulb were used for SEM
174 analysis. The hair strand and root were mounted onto a stub before silver coating under a

175 vacuum. A silver layer of 10 nm was deposited on each hair strand and root. Secondary electron
176 images were obtained along the length of each sample at an acceleration voltage of 15 kV.

177 **2.4.4. Dyed hair sample preparation**

178 Dyed hair was examined to check the persistence of hair dyes on the scalp as well as
179 hair shaft. The first step of this study was dyeing hair with oxidative and non-oxidative hair
180 dyes. For this purpose two volunteers (I and II) from the research group applied the selected
181 hair dyes on their hair. Volunteer 'I' applied oxidative while 'II' used non-oxidative hair dye.
182 Samples from both volunteers were collected daily for a period of ten days from the day of hair
183 dye application. As volunteer 'III' was applying non-oxidative hair dye therefore, it was not
184 included in this study.

185 For the purpose of sample collection, the scalp region i.e., frontal, parietal, temporal,
186 vertex and occipital was divided into 10 zones and marked as 'i-x' in which 'i' was the frontal
187 region and 'x' was the occipital region of the scalp (**Figure 1**). The 10 zones correspond to 10
188 day of sampling i.e., the swab was taken from 'i' on day 1 and 'x' on day 10. Each zone of the
189 scalp was approximately measured in 4×4 cm using a measurement tape for sample collection.
190 Hair that comes in this area was exactly clipped at the centre of the hair lengthwise. For sample
191 collection, swab technique was employed where cotton balls of 100 mg were soaked in 5 mL
192 of Type-I ultrapure water. Swab samples were collected from the designated zone and its
193 corresponding hair. Swab from hair corresponding to the zone marked on the scalp was
194 collected from approximately 8 cm above the scalp, which was taken approximately from 4×4
195 cm area, i.e. 8-12 cm of hair strand. Samples collected from scalp and hair strands were marked
196 as 'S-1' and 'S-2', respectively and the cotton ball was squeezed with forceps. The cotton ball
197 was finally washed with 5 mL methanol and both washes were mixed and filtered using 0.45
198 µm nylon membrane filter and chromatographed individually.

199 3. Result and discussion

200 3.1. Optimization of the detection conditions

201 The first part associated with chromatographic method development is the selection of
202 a sensitive detector. The selection of detection mode is based on the properties of selected
203 analytes. For the present study, the selected analytes i.e., HQ, RS, p-PPD and m-AMP were
204 found to be UV active due to the presence of conjugated, saturated and unsaturated bonds. They
205 also contain heteroatoms such as nitrogen and oxygen, which helps to increase their sensitivity
206 in the UV region. Based on UV spectroscopic analysis the λ_{\max} recorded for HQ was 222 and
207 290 (**Figure 1Sa**), RS was 220 and 275 (**Figure 1Sb**), m-AMP was 203 and 283 (**Figure 1Sc**)
208 and p-PPD was 203 and 240 (**Figure 1Sd**). As all the compounds showed two λ_{\max} i.e., below
209 220 and below 290. It was decided to carry out the further study by selecting the wavelengths
210 290, 275, 240, 283 for HQ, RS, p-PPD and m-AMP, respectively.

211 3.2. Optimization of pH of the mobile phase

212 In MLC charges on the analyte plays a significant role in the separation behaviour of analyte.
213 This is simply achieved by adjusting the pH of mobile phase with pKa of analyte [21]. The pKa
214 value provides an idea about ionic and non-ionic characteristics of the analyte. The pKa value
215 of HQ and RS are 9.9 and 9.3 and it is due to the fact that both possess OH⁻ charge. In the
216 working pH range of column (3-7) [22] both the compounds act as neutral at pH 7 due to their
217 pKa values. On the other hand, m-AMP (pKa; 4.3) and p-PPD (pKa; 6.2) have NH₂ groups that
218 are protonated (NH₃⁺) at pH 3 and pH 5 and neutral (NH₂) at pH 7. To study the behaviour of
219 compounds under the effect of pH the selected analytes were chromatographed at pH 3, 5 and
220 7. At pH 3 these compounds have more positive charge in comparison to pH 5 which is
221 responsible for increased retention time (Rt). However, using pH 5 the Rt decreased but it was
222 not as remarkable as compared to pH 7. The possible explanation to this could be that at pH 7

223 analytes are more likely to behave as a neutral compound, so the retention time of analytes
224 drastically decreased compared to pH 3 or pH 5. Based on the above facts pH 7 was selected
225 as the optimum pH for further study.

226 **3.3. Optimization of SDS concentration**

227 Based on common surfactants a SDS was selected due to its novelty and working with
228 this technique. Critical micellar concentration (CMC) plays an important role because at this
229 concentration maximum surfactant forms micelles and to achieve the best result the range of
230 SDS should be between 0.05 to 0.15 M. For the selected compounds when the concentration
231 of SDS was fixed at 0.05 M, p-PPD and m-AMP did not elute until 8 min. Talking about HQ
232 it did not show marked variation in Rt upon varying SDS concentration from 0.05 - 0.15 M.
233 When the concentration of SDS was raised to 0.15 M both the analytes eluted out within 4 min.
234 but using high strength of SDS the peak resolution was poor. Based on the above results, it was
235 decided to conduct further chromatographic analysis using 0.09 M SDS where the retention
236 time clocked by the separating analytes was below 6 min.

237 **3.4. Optimization of type and volume of organic modifiers**

238 In the present work the analytes were slightly non-polar and did get eluted at acceptable
239 chromatographic time using pure micellar mobile phase. Therefore, to enhance
240 chromatographic parameters i.e. efficiency (N) and asymmetry factor (B/A) a small amount of
241 organic modifier i.e. 2% 1-butanol was added to the micellar mobile phase. Using pure mobile
242 phase the chromatographic analysis generally shows poor chromatographic parameters like.
243 Rt, N and B/A. To improve both parameters a short-chain alcohol i.e., 1-propanol, 1-butanol
244 and 1-pentanol were added (**Figure 2Sa-d**). The selection of organic modifiers also depends
245 on log P value of the analyte to be chromatographed.

246

247 **3.5. Method validation**

248 Validation is one of the important step in any analytical method development. For the
249 present work the method was validated based on the guidelines described in Eurachem Method
250 validation guidelines (EURCHEM Guide, 2014) [23,24]. The studied validation parameters
251 were linearity, the limit of detection and quantification, intraday and interday accuracy as well
252 as precision and robustness.

253 **3.5.1. Calibration range, linearity and sensitivity**

254 Calibration study was performed using seven different concentrations of selected
255 analytes in the range of 0.08-10 µg/mL prepared using a micellar medium (**Figure 2a-d**).
256 Calibration curves were constructed using the average peak area versus concentration. The
257 slope, intercept, coefficient of determination (r^2) and residual standard deviation (RSD) were
258 calculated by the least square linear regression method.

259 The limit of detection was calculated with a minimum concentration of selected
260 analytes which generates a response significantly different from the noise of the baseline [25].
261 Calculation of LOD for HQ, RS, p-PPD and m-AMP were based on 3s criteria. LOQ was
262 calculated using 10s criteria which is the lowest concentration of analytes that could be
263 quantified with acceptable accuracy and precision. The obtained values of LOD and LOQ for
264 selected analytes were in the range of 0.04-0.09 µg/mL and 0.08-0.30 µg/mL respectively for
265 all samples (**Table 1**).

266 To study the selectivity of the developed method real matrix (blank hair dye
267 formulations and hair swab sample) were injected into the chromatographic system. The
268 purpose of the study was to see the effect of matrix on the elution time of the selected
269 compounds. As observed from the chromatograms of blank samples peaks corresponding to
270 the endogenous compounds eluted before 3.0 min. and no peaks were detected thereafter. The

271 chromatograms corresponding to blank hair dye formulations (**Figure 3a**) and hair swab
272 (**Figure 3b**) have been shown in **Figure 3**. Chromatograms obtained from the analysis of
273 spiked samples of hair dye formulation (**Figure 4a**) and hair swab (**Figure 4b**) are shown in
274 **Figure 4**.

275 **3.5.2. Precision and accuracy**

276 The intra-day and inter-day precision of the method was studied by injecting the
277 analytes at three different concentrations i.e. near to quantification limit, middle of the
278 calculated values and upper quantification limit (**Table 2**) which were injected on the same
279 day. Similarly, the intra-day analysis was determined based on six replicates analyzed over two
280 months by different analysts in random order. The precision of the developed method shown
281 as a percentage of relative standard deviation (% RSD) was < 5.6 %. The accuracy of the
282 method was measured by % recovery which was in the range of 91-105% for all the selected
283 compounds (**Table 2**). The results showed that the proposed method is suitable for analyzing
284 selected compounds in hair dye formulation and hair swab samples.

285 **3.5.3. Robustness of the method**

286 The robustness of the developed method was evaluated by performing small changes
287 in mobile phase composition i.e., SDS; 0.08-0.1 M, 1-butanol; 1.9-2.1%, pH; 6.5-7.5 and flow
288 rate; 0.9-1.1 mL/min. for all the analytes. The RSD% was obtained for changes in the area of
289 the peak and resolution. The retention times of analytes were calculated and the observed
290 difference was less than < 5.8%. Based on RSD% values, it could be observed that the studied
291 parameters had no significant effect on the resolution, peak area and Rt of analytes. Therefore
292 the method was robust enough to withstand any minor changes made in the chromatographic
293 parameters.

294 **3.6. Analytical results**

295 3.6.1. Analysis of marketed hair dyes formulations

296 . In order to detect the presence of different toxic compounds in hair colour the
297 developed method was applied to twenty-one (21) hair dyes marketed under different brand
298 names which were either non-oxidative or oxidative in nature. Out of 21 samples, **fourteen**
299 (14) hair dyes were of non-oxidative nature and **seven** (7) were oxidative.

300 Out of fourteen (14) non-oxidative hair dyes, five black and six brown (**Figure 5a**) hair
301 dyes were found to be positive for p-PPD. It is pertinent to mention here that only two samples
302 coded as NNH BL and PKM had mentioned p-PPD as one of the contents in the ingredient list.
303 The positive hair dye samples contained p-PPD in the range of 253 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (further diluted to
304 obtain the concentration of 15 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) to 134 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (further diluted to obtain the concentration
305 of 12 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) (**Figure 6c**). The EU regulation (EC No 1223/2009) of cosmetic products
306 (amended in 2013) has specified that the concentration of p-PPD applied to hair shafts should
307 not exceed 2% (calculated as free base) after mixing under oxidative conditions [7].

308 m-AMP was detected in three black and one brown (**Figure 5a**) hair dyes in the range
309 of 2.3-3.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Regarding RS it was detected in two black hair dye samples with the highest
310 concentration of 5.6 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Two black non-oxidative hair dyes were also found to be positive
311 for HQ in the range of 0.09 to 2.34 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. As shown in **Table 3**, most oxidative hair dye
312 products correctly labelled the ingredients.

313 The selected oxidative hair dye sample included four black and three brown (**Figure**
314 **5b**) colour dyes and all of them were positive for p-PPD. The ingredients mentioned on packing
315 of all hair dyes mentioned p-PPD as one of the ingredients (1% of weight) except for IBN. Out
316 of seven samples, three samples abbreviated as GBN (93 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), IEDBR (307 $\mu\text{g/mL}$),
317 GEXBL (228 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) (**Figure 6a**) have shown high concentration of p-PPD against the
318 quantity claimed on the wrapper of packing. All the analyzed samples which have shown the

319 presence of p-PPD out of the calibration range were further diluted to 12 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ concentration
320 to make them plausible. Regarding HQ many dye manufacturers had not claimed the presence
321 of HQ in the ingredient list, but they were positive for HQ in the range of 0.06- 23 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$.
322 Talking about RS only one brown hair dye sample was found to be positive for it (labelled on
323 five hair dye samples). Three brown and two black samples tested positive for m-AMP.
324 However, m-AMP was mentioned only on one sample without its concentration (**Table 3**). All
325 positive samples contain m-AMP in the range of 4.1 - 24 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ (further diluted to obtain the
326 concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). In most of the hair dye formulations two to three selected analytes
327 were detected simultaneously (**Figure 6b**).

328 **3.6.2. Analysis of hair swab**

329 Five volunteers from the research group were selected for the present study but the hair
330 swab was collected only from volunteers and 'I' and 'II'. As per *section 2.4.4*, hair swab
331 collected from a volunteer 'I' (applied oxidative hair dye) was injected into the chromatographic
332 system. The collected swab from both parts named as 'S-1' and 'S-2' of the hair was found
333 positive only for p-PPD. **Figure 7 a and b** showed that 'S-1' has a low concentration of p-PPD
334 in comparison to 'S-2' (oxidative hair dye). The study was conducted for ten days, but p-PPD
335 was only detected on the first and second day. It is worth mentioning that hair was not washed
336 during the sample collection period. Therefore only excess dye molecules which adhered to the
337 cuticle leached out. After two days, no p-PPD was detected in the swab.

338 The analytical data obtained from hair swabs 'S-1' and 'S-2' (dyed with non-oxidative
339 dye) of volunteer 'II' was positive for p-PPD and m-AMP both. After the application of dye,
340 hair was only washed under running water and no shampoo, soap and hair oil were used. From
341 day one to five, the amount of p-PPD and m-AMP decreased almost at a constant rate.
342 However, on the sixth day, when hair was washed with shampoo using mild hot water the
343 highest concentration for p-PPD and m-AMP was reported. Because hot water opens the

344 cuticles of hair and dye molecules which were adhered escape from there this is the reason for
345 increased concentration. Then on successive days concentration of both analytes decreased.
346 The obtained results have been shown for p-PPD in **Figure 8 a and c** and m-AMP in **Figure 8**
347 **b and d**.

348 **3.6.3. Scanning electron microscope analysis of dyed hair**

349 Apart from chemical analysis in the present work it was also decided to study the
350 physical damage caused by the regular use of dyes for the purpose of colouring of hair. In the
351 present study hair shaft and root of five volunteers (I-V) aged between 25-35 were examined
352 by SEM to assess the damage caused to the hair shaft due to the application of hair dyes [26,
353 27]. Volunteers 'I-III' frequently use dyes to colour their hair. Based on the questionnaire filled
354 by the volunteers, it was observed that volunteers 'I-III' were dyeing, bleaching and not
355 nourishing hair with any kind of hair oil. However, volunteers 'IV' and 'V' were using hair oil
356 as well as were also dyeing their hair (**Table 4**). Many researchers have reported that dyeing
357 of hair roughens the hair surfaces as well as the cuticle scales are damaged and inclined
358 outwards. Volunteers who were frequently dyeing their hair were more vulnerable to damage.

359 In the present study different hair shafts were observed under SEM and
360 microphotographed to study the hair shaft damage. Volunteers 'IV' and 'V' acted as our control
361 as the volunteer never used any dye and nourished the hair with hair oil regularly so healthy
362 cuticles were observed during SEM analysis and no splitting was revealed (**Figure 9a and b**)
363 in the hair sample obtained from Volunteer 'IV' and 'V'. The surface of the hair shaft appeared
364 smooth and the root was healthy [27].

365 The SEM examination of the hair sample from the volunteer 'II' and 'III' who applied
366 non-oxidative hair dye but also used regular hair oil showed that cuticle scales were outward
367 inclined and irregular with moderate damage and cortex was not damaged in this case (**Figure**

368 **9c and d).** In case of volunteer 'I' who applied oxidative hair dyes, bleached hair and never
369 applied hair oil showed that hair root and shaft were severely damaged and no cuticle scales
370 were observed (**Figure 9e and f**). During the study, microphotographs from SEM revealed that
371 hair and root damage was moderate for those who were applying hair dyes but also nourishing
372 their hair with hair oil.

373 **4. Conclusion**

374 The micellar liquid chromatographic method has been successfully optimized and
375 validated for simultaneous determination of HQ, RS, p-PPD and m-AMP in oxidative and non-
376 oxidative hair dyes formulations and hair swab samples obtained from volunteers. The
377 advantage of the developed method is the possibility of direct injection of hair dyes samples
378 into the chromatographic system after centrifugation and filtration, avoiding long and tedious
379 extraction procedures. All four analytes were separated and detected in different sample matrix
380 within 7 min. with satisfactory precision and accuracy (< 5.6 %). The method validation was
381 accomplished using Eurachem method validation guidelines with satisfactory results in
382 linearity, limit of detection, limit of quantitation, precision, accuracy and robustness. The
383 linearity range and LOQs were sufficient to detect all selected compounds in hair dye
384 formulation.

385 The developed method meets the criteria of 'green chemistry' as a low amount of
386 organic solvents has been used. Some of the other noteworthy advantage of the method is that
387 it is relatively inexpensive compared to other chromatographic methods (HPLC, LC-MS or
388 GC-MS). Apart from detecting selected analytes in hair dye formulation, the study also
389 included analysis of hair swab samples from volunteer who used oxidative and non-oxidative
390 hair dye which were collected for up to ten days from the day of application of dye on the hair.
391 This study was conducted to determine the persistence of hair dye molecules on scalp and hair.
392 It has been found that oxidative hair dye was detected only on the first day of analysis while

393 non-oxidative hair dyes persisted till ten days with measurable quantity. Study was also
394 conducted to see the damage caused on the hair surface due to dye treatment given to hair.
395 Scanning electron microscopic results showed that the hair damage was severe for those who
396 frequently applied hair dyes. Therefore it could be concluded that there is a need to create
397 awareness among hair dye users about the presence of toxic compounds which are being used
398 in hair dye formulations and which may pose severe health issues to its users. Due to the lack
399 of strict regulation in India, there is also a need to regularly monitor the concentration of toxic
400 compounds in hair dye formulation. It should also be noted that formulations of strict laws is
401 highly needed for the monitorization of hair dyes in Asia.

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409 5. References

- 410 [1] M. Ridder, Market value of hair dye/color worldwide in 2019 and 2025 (in million U.S.
411 dollars), (2020).[https://www.statista.com/statistics/972997/global-hair-color-market-](https://www.statista.com/statistics/972997/global-hair-color-market-value/)
412 [value/](https://www.statista.com/statistics/972997/global-hair-color-market-value/) (accessed November 14, 2020).
- 413 [2] S.A. da França, M.F. Dario, V.B. Esteves, A.R. Baby, M.V.R. Velasco, Types of hair
414 dye and their mechanisms of action, *Cosmetics.*, 2 (2015) 110–126.
415 <https://doi.org/10.3390/cosmetics2020110>.
- 416 [3] D. Lewis, J. Mama, J. Hawkes, A review of aspects of oxidative hair dye chemistry with
417 special reference to n-nitrosamine formation, *Materials (Basel)*. 6 (2013) 517–534.
418 <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma6020517>.
- 419 [4] P. Phadatare Suvarna, N. Nesari Tanuja, D. Pokharkar, R.P. Pingle, M.S. Gadge,
420 Comparative study of dyeing efficiency and retention capacity of herbal hair dyes, *Int.*
421 *J. Res. Ayurveda Pharm.* 4 (2013).198–202. <https://doi.org/10.7897/2277-4343.04221>.
- 422 [5] C. Burnett, M.M. Jacobs, A. Seppala, P. Shubik, Evaluation of the toxicity and
423 carcinogenicity of hair dyes, *J. Toxicol. Environ. Health.*, 6 (1980) 247–257.
424 <https://doi.org/10.1080/15287398009529849>.
- 425 [6] H. Sosted, T. Menné, J.D. Johansen, Patch test dose-response study of p-
426 phenylenediamine: Thresholds and anatomical regional differences, *Con Der.*, 54 (2006)
427 145-149. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0105-1873.2006.00803.x>.
- 428 [7] The European commission, commission regulation (EU) 2019/831 amending annexes
429 II, III and V to regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 of the European parliament and of the
430 council on cosmetic products, *Comm. Regul.* 2019/831. 2019 (2019) 1–35.
- 431 [8] B.H. Shao, X.Z. Xu, J.W. Yan, Quantitative determination of commercial oxidation hair
432 dyes by reversed-phase HPLC, *J. Liq. Chromatogr. Relat. Technol.* 24 (2001) 241–249.
433 <https://doi.org/10.1081/JLC-100001485>.

- 434 [9] A. Chisvert, A. Cháfer, A. Salvador, Hair dyes in cosmetics: regulatory aspects and
435 analytical methods, *Anal. Cosmet. Prod.* 6 (2007) 190–209. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-044452260-3/50033-4>.
436
- 437 [10] J.H. Franco, B.F. Da Silva, M.V.B. Zanoni, Assessment of semipermanent hair dyes in
438 wash water from beauty salons by liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry-
439 selected reaction monitoring (LC-MS/MS-SRM), *Anal. Methods.* 12 (2020) 5415–5423.
440 <https://doi.org/10.1039/d0ay01395a>.
- 441 [11] L.H. Wang, S.J. Tsai, Simultaneous determination of oxidative hair dye p-
442 phenylenediamine and its metabolites in human and rabbit biological fluids, *Anal.*
443 *Biochem.* 312 (2003) 201–207. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-2697\(02\) 00501-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-2697(02) 00501-8).
- 444 [12] H.J. Zhu, Y.W. Yang, An efficient and rapid thin-layer chromatography method for the
445 identification of 32 dye substances in hair dye products, *Int. J. Cosmet. Sci.* 36 (2014)
446 369–378. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ics.12135>.
- 447 [13] M.L. Di Gioia, A. Leggio, A. Le Pera, A. Liguori, A. Napoli, Determination by gas
448 chromatography/mass spectrometry of p-phenylenediamine in hair dyes after conversion
449 to an imine derivative, *J. Chromatogr. A.* 1066 (2005) 143–148.
450 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2005.01.039>.
- 451 [14] Á.M. Móricz, V. Lapat, G.E. Morlock, High-performance thin-layer chromatography
452 hyphenated to high-performance liquid chromatography -mass spectrometry for
453 characterization of coeluting isomers, *Talanta.* 219 (2020) 9-13.
454 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta. 2020. 121306>.
- 455 [15] B. Goger, R. Wintersteiger, H. Beck, Determination of a hair dye using different
456 derivatization agents and HPLC in combination with UV, electrochemical, and
457 fluorescence detection, *Arch. Pharm.* 332 (1999) 399–404.
458 [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI))

- 459 [16] A. Meyer, B. Blömeke, K. Fischer, Determination of p-phenylenediamine and its
460 metabolites MAPPD and DAPPD in biological samples using HPLC-DAD and
461 amperometric detection, *J. Chromatogr. B* 877 (2009) 1627–1633. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jchromb.2009.04.008>.
- 463 [17] N.A. Penner, P.N. Nesterenko, Simultaneous determination of dihydroxybenzenes,
464 aminophenols and phenylenediamines in hair dyes by high-performance liquid
465 chromatography on hypercross-linked polystyrene, *Analyst*. 125 (2000) 1249–1254.
466 <https://doi.org/10.1039/b001524p>.
- 467 [18] P. Dugo, O. Favoino, P.Q. Tranchida, G. Dugo, L. Mondello, Off-line coupling of non-
468 aqueous reversed-phase and silver ion high-performance liquid chromatography-mass
469 spectrometry for the characterization of rice oil triacylglycerol positional isomers, *J.*
470 *Chromatogr. A.*, 1041 (2004) 135–142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2004.04.063>.
- 471 [19] M.J. Ruiz-Ángel, S. Carda-Broch, J.R. Torres-Lapasió, Retention mechanisms in
472 micellar liquid chromatography, *J. Chromatogr. A.*, 1216 (2009) 1798–1814.
473 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2008.09.053>.
- 474 [20] M.J. Ruiz-Angel, R.D. Caballero, E.F. Simoó-Alfonso, M.C. García-Alvarez-Coque,
475 Micellar liquid chromatography: Suitable technique for screening analysis, *J.*
476 *Chromatogr. A.*, 947 (2002) 31–45. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673\(01\)01595-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673(01)01595-3).
- 477 [21] M.M. Ayad, M.M. Hosny, A.E. Ibrahim, O.M. El-Abassy, F.F. Belal, An eco-friendly
478 micellar HPLC method for the simultaneous determination of triamterene and xipamide
479 in active pharmaceutical ingredients and marketed tablet dosage form, *Acta*
480 *Chromatogr.*, 33 (2021) 51–56. <https://doi.org/10.1556/1326.2020.00746>.
- 481 [22] J. Peris-Vicente, J. Esteve-Romero, S. Carda-Broch, Validation of analytical methods
482 based on chromatographic techniques: An overview, *Anal. Sep. Sci.*, 5 (2015) 1757–
483 1808. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9783527678129.assep064>.

- 484 [23] Eurachem guide , The fitness for purpose of analytical methods a laboratory guide to
485 method validation and related topics, [https://www.eurachem.org/
486 images/stories/Guides/pdf/MV_guide_2nd_ed_EN.pdf](https://www.eurachem.org/images/stories/Guides/pdf/MV_guide_2nd_ed_EN.pdf) (assessed 9 May 2021)
- 487 [24] J. da Silva Guedes, M.L. da Silva Guedes, Quantificação do indicador de Nelson de
488 Moraes (curva de mortalidade proporcional), Rev. Saude Publica. 40 (2006) 951–961.
489 <https://doi.org/10.1590/s0034-89102006000700002>.
- 490 [25] R.N. El-Shaheny, M.H. El-Maghrabey, F.F. Belal, Micellar liquid chromatography from
491 green analysis perspective, Open Chem. 13 (2015) 877–892.
492 <https://doi.org/10.1515/chem-2015-0101>.
- 493 [26] Y. Narisawa, K. Hashimoto, H. Kohda, Scanning electron microscopic observations of
494 extracted terminal hair follicles of the adult human scalp and eyebrow with special
495 references to the bulge area, Arch. Dermatol. Res. 287 (1995) 599–607.
496 <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00374083>.
- 497 [27] C.C. Alberts, B.H. Saranholi, F. Frei, P.M. Galetti, Comparing hair-morphology and
498 molecular methods to identify fecal samples from Neotropical felids, PLoS One. 12
499 (2017) 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0184073>.

500

501 **Figures**

502 **Figure 1.** Different regions of the scalp

503 **Figure 2 (a-d).** Calibration curve and chemical structures of selected analytes: (a) HQ
504 calibration curve; (b) RS calibration curve; (c) m-AMP calibration curve; (d) p-PPD
505 calibration curve in the optimized chromatographic conditions: mobile phase 0.09 M
506 SDS-2% 1-butanol (v/v) pH 7, flow rate 1 mL/min., injection volume 20 μ L

507 **Figure 3 (a-b)** Chromatograms of blank matrix (a) Chromatogram of blank oxidative hair dye;
508 (b) Chromatogram of blank non-oxidative hair dye; in the optimized chromatographic
509 conditions: mobile phase 0.09 M SDS-2% 1-butanol (v/v) pH 7, flow rate 1 mL/min.,
510 injection volume 20 μ L

511 **Figure 4 (a-b)** Chromatograms obtained by spiking standard solution of analyte (a)
512 Chromatogram of spiked oxidative hair dye; (b) Chromatogram of spiked non-
513 oxidative hair dye; in the optimized chromatographic conditions: mobile phase 0.09
514 M SDS-2% 1-butanol (v/v) pH 7, flow rate 1 mL/min., injection volume 20 μ L,
515 detection at 254 nm

516 **Figure 5 (a-b)** Graph showing black and brown hair dyes found positive for selected analytes:
517 (a) Non-oxidative hair dye; (b) Oxidative hair dye

518 **Figure 6 (a-c)** Chromatograms of the real hair dye formulations (a) Chromatogram of sample
519 number 20 (oxidative); (b) Chromatogram of sample number 18 (oxidative); (c)
520 Chromatogram of Sample number 7 (non-oxidative) in the optimized
521 chromatographic conditions: mobile phase 0.09 M SDS-2% 1-butanol (v/v) pH 7, flow
522 rate 1 mL/min., injection volume 20 μ L

523 **Figure 7 (a-b)** The concentration of p-PPD in the dyed hair (oxidative hair dye) swab: (a) Swab
524 from root part of hair; (b) Swab from 8 cm above hair root

525 **Figure 8 (a-d)** The concentration of p-PPD and m-AMP (a) Swab from hair scalp (p-PPD); (b)
526 Swab from hair scalp (m-AMP); (c) Swab from 8 cm above scalp (p-PPD); (d) Swab
527 from 8 cm above scalp (m-AMP) in the dyed hair (non-oxidative hair dye) swab

528 **Figure 9 (a-f)** Scanning electron photomicrographs of studied hair: (a) Hair shaft of normal
529 hair; (b) Root of normal hair; (c) Shaft of moderately damaged hair; (d) Root of
530 moderately damaged hair; (e) Shaft of damaged hair; (f) Root of damaged hair hair

531 **Figure 1S (a-d)** UV spectra of selected analytes: (a) UV spectra of hydroquinone; (b) UV
532 spectra of resorcinol; (c) UV spectra of p-phenylenediamine; (d) UV spectra of m-
533 aminophenol

534 **Figure 2S (a-d)** Chromatograms of standard compounds: (a) Chromatogram of
535 hydroquinone; (b) Chromatogram of resorcinol; (c) Chromatogram of p-
536 phenylenediamine; (d) Chromatogram of m-aminophenol in the optimized
537 chromatographic conditions: mobile phase 0.09 M SDS-2% 1-butanol (v/v) pH 7,
538 flow rate 1 mL/min., injection volume 20 μ L

539